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Financialization of Commodity Markets in India: Evidence from the VARMA-DCC-GARCH Model

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Abstract: *This study investigates the financialization phenomenon in Indian commodity futures markets using a market integration approach. Daily data covering eight commodity futures namely Crude Oil, Natural Gas, Gold, Silver, Aluminium, Zinc, Lead, and Nickel alongside three financial market indices (BSE100, INR/USD, CCIL Liquid Bond Index) are examined. Employing the VARMA-DCC-GARCH model, we analyse return and volatility spillovers, dynamic conditional correlations, time-varying hedge ratios, and optimal portfolio weights. The VARMA-DCC-GARCH model reveals substantial volatility spillover from equity, forex, and bond markets to most commodity futures, while the reverse spillover is primarily confined to Crude Oil, Zinc, and Lead. These findings provide evidence of moderate financialization in Indian commodity markets—lower than in developed markets but comparable to China. Gold functions as a safe-haven asset, while base metals serve as diversifiers. Hedge ratios and portfolio weights vary considerably around the 2008–09 Global Financial Crisis and COVID-19, highlighting the importance of dynamic portfolio strategies.*

Keywords: Financialization; Commodity Futures; DCC-GARCH; Volatility Spillover; India; Portfolio Diversification; Safe Haven

1 Introduction

With finite diversification opportunities across financial markets, investors have increasingly explored alternative investment options [1]. In recent decades, financial investors have appreciable interest in commodity markets owing to their hedging and portfolio risk management properties. Investment in commodity markets escalated in developed countries since the 1990s and in developing countries following the commodity boom of 2000, driven by demand from emerging economies like China and India [2]. Two principal reasons underpin this growth. First, commodity and financial asset prices are determined by different factors, generating negative correlations. Second, commodities act as inflation hedges [3, 4, 5].

With more investors capitalising on this opportunity, commodity prices surged continuously but reversed following the Lehman crisis of 2008 [2]. As a result, the commodity market became substantially influenced by financial investors, resulting in a significant relationship between commodity and financial capital markets [6, 7, 8]. Moreover, commodity prices are also appreciably influenced by financial capital markets [9, 10, 11], leading to the widely discussed phenomenon of the “financialization of commodities.”¹

* Corresponding author. This paper is part of my thesis, submitted for the award of degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Economics.

¹ “The financialization process refers to a situation wherein the prices of individual commodities are not only determined by their primary factors of demand and supply, but also by several financial factors and investors’ behaviour in the derivative markets” [7].

While evidence of financialization is prominent in developed countries, this issue has received only peripheral attention in developing countries. [12] reported evidence of financialization in the Chinese commodity market. By contrast, [2] found that Indian commodity markets appear relatively insulated from financialization due to strict regulatory mechanisms. Although the Indian commodity market has been active since the launch of nationalised exchanges in 2003, very few studies have examined the interlinkages between Indian commodity and financial markets [13, 14]. This study fills that gap by employing the Dynamic Conditional Correlation (DCC) model [15].

This study contributes to existing literature in three ways. First, it distinctly analyses the financialization of energy, precious metal, and base metal futures. Second, it examines integration with the stock, bond, and foreign exchange markets. Third, time-varying hedge ratios and optimal portfolio weights are estimated to assess investment sensitivity during crisis periods.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3 describes the methodology. Section 4 presents the data. Section 5 discusses empirical results. Section 6 concludes with policy implications.

2 Literature Review

In the past few decades, financial investors have become increasingly involved in commodity markets, and commodities have become indispensable to financial hedging and investment [6, 7, 8]. Following the burst of the dot-com bubble in 2000 and the subsequent commodity boom, researchers were encouraged to examine financialization using diverse datasets and econometric techniques [16, 17, 18, 8]. These studies highlighted that investors secured risk diversification benefits from commodity futures.

[7] used the DCC-GARCH method to analyse long-run relationships between 25 strategic commodity price returns and equity markets (2001–2011), finding that correlations change over time and are highly volatile, especially after the 2008 crisis. [19] employed a VAR-GARCH framework to examine correlations and volatility spillovers between the S&P 500 and commodity indices (energy, food, gold, beverages) over 2000–2011.

[20] found that integration of commodity and conventional asset markets may cause systematic shocks to progressively dominate commodity returns. Many studies confirm that a higher degree of co-movement diminishes diversification benefits [16, 21], although contrary findings are reported by [22] and [5]. Commodities are generally considered useful tools for strategic asset allocation due to their low return correlations with traditional asset classes [18, 23, 24].

Several studies have emphasised a time-varying correlation pattern between financial and commodity markets [25, 26], while others argue that financialization is confined to economic downturns [16, 27]. Co-movements between stock market and commodity prices were not uniform, with notable exceptions in bullion and metals markets where conflicting findings pointed to regime transitions [28, 7].

For the Indian commodity market, studies have primarily focused on price discovery and efficiency [29, 30]. [31] and [32] found evidence of volatility clustering in gold and crude oil markets. [14] examined contagion effects between Indian asset markets. The present study aims to comprehensively examine the financialization of Indian commodity futures markets through a market integration approach, incorporating crisis periods including the COVID-19 pandemic.

3 Methodology

Multivariate GARCH models have been widely used to study the volatility dynamics of financial markets, including commodity markets [7, 1, 12]. The econometric specification has two components: a Vector Autoregression (VAR) with one lag to model return dynamics, and

a multivariate GARCH model for time-varying variances and covariances. The conditional variance is assumed to follow a VARMA-GARCH(1,1) process.

3.1 Mean Equation

$$r_{it} = m_{i0} + \sum_{j=1}^2 m_{ij} r_{jt-1} + \epsilon_{it}, \quad \epsilon_{it} | I_{t-1} \sim N(0, h_{it}), \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{it} = v_{it} h_{it}^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad v_{it} \sim N(0, 1) \quad (2)$$

In equation 1, r_{it} denotes the return series for asset i and ϵ_{it} is the random error term with conditional variance h_{it} . I_{t-1} denotes the market information available at time $t - 1$. The relation between the error term ϵ_{it} and the conditional variance h_{it} is specified in equation 2.

3.2 DCC-GARCH Model

In two steps, the [15] DCC model is estimated. The GARCH parameters are estimated in the first stage; in the second stage, the correlation is estimated. The bivariate DCC model's conditional covariance matrix is:

$$H_t = D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} R_t D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} D_t &= \begin{pmatrix} h_{11,t}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & h_{22,t}^2 \end{pmatrix} \\ R_t &= Q_t^{*-\frac{1}{2}} Q_t Q_t^{*-\frac{1}{2}}, \quad Q_t^* = \begin{pmatrix} q_{11,t} & 0 \\ 0 & q_{22,t} \end{pmatrix} \\ Q_t &= (1 - \theta_1 - \theta_2) \bar{Q} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} \epsilon_{t-1}^T + \theta_2 Q_{t-1} \\ \bar{Q} &= \text{cov}(\epsilon_t \epsilon_{t-1}^T) = E(\epsilon_t \epsilon_{t-1}^T) \end{aligned}$$

The full conditional covariance matrix is thus:

$$H_t = \begin{bmatrix} h_{11,t} & h_{12,t} \\ h_{21,t} & h_{22,t} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{h_{11,t}} & \sqrt{h_{12,t}} \\ \sqrt{h_{21,t}} & \sqrt{h_{22,t}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12,t} \\ \rho_{21,t} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{h_{11,t}} & 0 \\ 0 & \sqrt{h_{22,t}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The dynamic correlation matrix ρ_t is:

$$\rho_t = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho_{12,t} \\ \rho_{21,t} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{q_{12t}}{\sqrt{q_{11t} q_{22t}}} \\ \frac{q_{12t}}{\sqrt{q_{11t} q_{22t}}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

3.3 Risk Hedging

The conditional volatility estimates can be used to construct hedge ratios [33]. A long position in asset i can be hedged with a short position in asset j . The hedge ratio between asset i and asset j is:

$$B_{ijt} = \frac{h_{ijt}}{h_{jtt}}$$

3.4 Portfolio Weights

The conditional volatilities from the GARCH models can also be used to construct optimal portfolio weights [34]:

$$w_{ij,t} = \frac{h_{jj,t} - h_{ij,t}}{h_{ii,t} - 2h_{ij,t} + h_{jj,t}}$$

$$w_{ij,t} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } w_{ij,t} < 0 \\ w_{ij,t}, & \text{if } 0 \leq w_{ij,t} \leq 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } w_{ij,t} > 1 \end{cases}$$

In constructing portfolio weights between two assets, $w_{ij,t}$ is the weight of asset i in a one-rupee portfolio at time t ; $h_{ij,t}$ is the conditional covariance between assets i and j ; $h_{jj,t}$ is the conditional variance of asset j ; and the weight of asset j is $1 - w_{ij,t}$.

4 Data and Descriptive Statistics

The dataset includes daily prices of four asset classes: commodity futures, bond market, foreign exchange, and equity/stock market. Commodity futures price data are sourced from the Multi Commodity Exchange of India (MCX), which holds approximately 96.8% of the market share in commodity futures trading by value. Eight commodity futures are included: Crude Oil (CO), Natural Gas (NG), Gold (GD), Silver (SR), Aluminium (AL), Zinc (ZC), Lead (LD), and Nickel (NL). Bond market data (CCIL Liquid Bond Index—five most actively traded government bonds) are obtained from the Clearing Corporation of India Limited (CCIL). Stock market performance is measured by the BSE100 Index (Bombay Stock Exchange). The INR/USD exchange rate is collected from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI).

The sample period spans April 3, 2006, to March 31, 2022 (3,677–3,679 observations per series), covering the 2008–09 Global Financial Crisis, the 2010–12 Eurozone crisis, the rupee devaluation, and the COVID-19 pandemic. Continuously compounded daily returns are calculated as $100 \times \ln(P_t/P_{t-1})$, where P_t is the daily closing price.

Table 1: Basic Statistics

Statistics/Variables	Crude Oil	Natural Gas	Gold	Silver	Aluminium
Mean	0.028	0.001	0.047	0.032	0.02
Median	0.054	-0.049	0.04	0.065	0.000
Maximum	31.894	24.473	8.119	8.859	10.543
Minimum	-34.573	-16.199	-9.469	-16.702	-9.411
Std. Dev.	2.588	3.13	1.05	1.726	1.322
Skewness	-0.375	0.484	-0.347	-0.657	0.161
Kurtosis	30.868	7.19	11.617	9.983	7.557
Jarque-Bera	119073.1 (0.000)	2835.288 (0.000)	11455.9 (0.000)	7739.23 (0.000)	3199.537 (0.000)
ARCH-LM Test(10)	67.539 (0.000)	16.351 (0.000)	21.342 (0.000)	19.976 (0.000)	19.123 (0.000)
ARCH-LM Test(20)	43.802 (0.000)	10.303 (0.000)	12.176 (0.000)	11.011 (0.000)	10.167 (0.000)
Observations	3677	3679	3679	3679	3679

Tables 1 and 2 report descriptive statistics. Mean and median values are close to zero for all series. Gold records the highest average return (0.047%), followed by BSE100 (0.040%), Silver (0.032%), and Crude Oil (0.028%). Natural Gas records the lowest (0.001%). Standard deviations are considerably lower for the Bond Index (0.358%) and Forex (0.473%) than for Natural Gas (3.130%) and Crude Oil (2.588%), reflecting the stabilising role of government regulation. All return series exhibit excess kurtosis and non-normality (Jarque-Bera, $p < 0.001$). ARCH(10) and ARCH(20) statistics confirm conditional heteroscedasticity in all series satisfying the necessary condition for multivariate GARCH modelling.

Figures 1 and 2 show the daily prices. Commodity prices reflected a uniform pattern of decline during the 2008–09 crisis and COVID-19, with exceptions for Gold, Lead, and Aluminium. Stock prices plummeted alongside rupee depreciation and a fall in the Bond Index during 2008–09.

Table 2: Basic Statistics

Statistics/Variables	Zinc	Lead	Nickel	BSE100	US\$/INR	Bond Index
Mean	0.013	0.023	0.017	0.04	0.015	0.03
Median	0.028	0.000	0.000	0.083	0.000	0.032
Maximum	9.363	17.998	53.208	15.49	4.020	5.253
Minimum	-10.888	-12.982	-15.853	-13.881	-3.006	-5.739
Std. Dev.	1.754	1.893	2.221	1.419	0.473	0.358
Skewness	-0.094	0.209	3.758	-0.283	0.171	-0.65
Kurtosis	5.938	12.331	95.223	15.337	8.244	47.241
Jarque-Bera	1328.36 (0.000)	13374.24 (0.000)	1312427 (0.000)	23381.3 (0.000)	4233.942 (0.000)	300286.7 (0.000)
ARCH-LM	27.88	13.57	52.129	59.672	58.894	16.053
Test(10)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
ARCH-LM	15.583	8.6023	29.784	30.672	34.118	10.635
Test(20)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)
Observations	3679	3679	3679	3679	3679	3679

Figure 1: Time Series Plots of Commodity Prices and Financial Market Indices

5 Results and Discussion

Before applying the multivariate GARCH models, we tested for heteroscedasticity using the LM statistic at 10 and 20 lags, confirming conditional heteroscedasticity and ARCH effects (volatility clustering) in all return series.

5.1 Unconditional Correlations

Table 3: Static unconditional correlation between returns of Market Indices and Commodities

Correlation	Crude Oil	Natural Gas	Gold	Silver	Aluminium	Zinc	Lead	Nickel
BSE100	0.121 (0.000)	-0.008 (0.629)	-0.089 (0.000)	0.064 (0.000)	0.056 (0.001)	0.130 (0.000)	0.110 (0.000)	0.097 (0.000)
US\$/INR	-0.008 (0.632)	0.071 (0.000)	0.069 (0.000)	-0.040 (0.016)	0.010 (0.564)	-0.026 (0.110)	-0.055 (0.001)	-0.045 (0.006)
Bond Index	-0.038 (0.020)	-0.020 (0.227)	-0.011 (0.505)	-0.020 (0.227)	-0.039 (0.017)	-0.011 (0.505)	-0.032 (0.052)	-0.020 (0.224)

Table 3 reports the static unconditional correlation matrix between market index returns and commodity returns. The correlation between BSE100 and commodity returns is positive and significant for most commodities, except Natural Gas (insignificant) and Gold (-0.089), consistent with Gold's hedging capability.² The direct association with stock returns is relatively stronger for Zinc (0.130), Crude Oil (0.121), and Lead (0.110), while Aluminium, Silver, and Nickel exhibit low positive correlations, classifying them as diversifiers. In the forex market, Lead, Nickel, and Silver emerge as potential hedging assets, while Gold and Natural Gas act as diversifiers. For the bond market, Aluminium, Crude Oil, and Lead report negative significant associations with the Bond Index, implying hedging properties.

5.2 Multivariate GARCH Models

Tables 4-6 report the VARMA-DCC-GARCH estimates. The DCC models document substantial evidence of short-run (α_{21}) and long-run (β_{21}) volatility spillovers from all three financial markets that are equity, forex, and bond to all commodity futures. The reverse spillover is primarily confined to Crude Oil, Zinc, and Lead. These results provide evidence of the financialization of Indian commodity futures markets, consistent with [35], [19], [36], and [37].

Regarding return spillovers, current stock market returns are significantly influenced by their own lagged returns (L_{11}) in all models. Current commodity returns are generally unresponsive to lagged stock market returns (L_{21}), except for Crude Oil, where higher lagged stock market returns lead to higher current Crude Oil returns. Current forex returns (L_{11}) are statistically insignificant; lagged bond returns positively affect current bond returns (L_{11}), and lagged commodity returns (except Gold) positively affect current bond returns (L_{12}).

5.3 Dynamic Conditional Correlations

Figure 2 depicts the time-varying DCC correlations between market indices and individual commodities. In all estimated VARMA-DCC-GARCH models, the sum of DCC coefficients $\theta_1 + \theta_2 < 1$, confirming mean-reverting dynamic correlations.

Energy Commodities: The correlation between BSE100 and Crude Oil is largely positive, intensifying during crisis episodes and briefly turning negative in 2013-14. Natural Gas exhibits a largely negative correlation with BSE100 and the Bond Market (with positive spikes during crises), supporting its use as a hedge for equity and bond investors.

² A hedge is an asset having a negative correlation with another asset, whereas a diversifier is an asset reporting a positive but relatively low correlation [14].

Table 4: VARMA-DCC GARCH Model Estimates (Stock Market and Commodities)

Variable	RCO	RNG	RGD	RSR	RAL	RZC	RLD	RNL
Mean Model (RBSE)								
μ_{10}	0.070 (0.000)	0.073 (0.000)	0.070 (0.000)	0.070 (0.000)	0.069 (0.000)	0.070 (0.000)	0.068 (0.000)	0.070 (0.000)
L_{11}	0.077 (0.000)	0.071 (0.000)	0.073 (0.000)	0.076 (0.000)	0.074 (0.000)	0.076 (0.000)	0.073 (0.000)	0.071 (0.000)
L_{12}	-0.008 (0.441)	0.001 (0.870)	-0.014 (0.481)	0.028 (0.006)	0.008 (0.548)	0.003 (0.806)	-0.004 (0.760)	0.002 (0.842)
Mean Model (RCO)								
μ_{20}	0.088 (0.004)	0.020 (0.669)	0.028 (0.036)	0.008 (0.733)	0.027 (0.170)	0.037 (0.168)	0.032 (0.235)	0.003 (0.893)
L_{21}	0.046 (0.123)	0.039 (0.268)	-0.008 (0.573)	-0.015 (0.569)	0.011 (0.459)	0.010 (0.608)	0.023 (0.280)	0.026 (0.356)
L_{22}	0.003 (0.873)	-0.018 (0.314)	-0.008 (0.719)	0.007 (0.724)	-0.015 (0.346)	0.006 (0.747)	0.008 (0.678)	-0.023 (0.513)
Variance Equation								
C_{11}	0.019 (0.000)	0.015 (0.000)	0.018 (0.035)	0.015 (0.008)	0.024 (0.014)	0.019 (0.002)	0.017 (0.009)	0.021 (0.391)
C_{21}	0.089 (0.007)	0.113 (0.000)	0.046 (0.156)	0.040 (0.120)	0.111 (0.029)	0.021 (0.013)	0.015 (0.017)	0.865 (0.001)
C_{22}	0.087 (0.000)	0.102 (0.000)	0.092 (0.000)	0.099 (0.000)	0.100 (0.000)	0.096 (0.000)	0.091 (0.000)	0.100 (0.000)
α_{11}	0.005 (0.002)	0.000 (0.012)	0.025 (0.237)	0.006 (0.087)	0.004 (0.408)	0.006 (0.109)	0.004 (0.248)	0.005 (0.363)
α_{12}	0.050 (0.078)	0.002 (0.527)	0.010 (0.300)	0.016 (0.304)	0.011 (0.328)	0.028 (0.050)	0.075 (0.000)	-0.009 (0.904)
α_{21}	0.106 (0.000)	0.066 (0.000)	0.108 (0.034)	0.057 (0.011)	0.081 (0.001)	0.039 (0.001)	0.010 (0.001)	0.225 (0.006)
α_{22}	0.907 (0.000)	0.888 (0.000)	0.894 (0.000)	0.886 (0.000)	0.892 (0.000)	0.893 (0.000)	0.899 (0.000)	0.891 (0.000)
β_{11}	-0.005 (0.002)	0.001 (0.000)	-0.015 (0.553)	0.000 (0.954)	-0.006 (0.412)	-0.003 (0.450)	-0.002 (0.711)	-0.004 (0.756)
β_{12}	-0.024 (0.239)	0.012 (0.001)	0.000 (0.973)	-0.008 (0.588)	0.010 (0.662)	-0.024 (0.023)	-0.079 (0.000)	0.328 (0.101)
β_{21}	0.875 (0.000)	0.921 (0.000)	0.837 (0.000)	0.926 (0.000)	0.836 (0.000)	0.953 (0.000)	0.989 (0.000)	0.460 (0.001)
θ_1	0.015 (0.201)	0.039 (0.081)	0.015 (0.003)	0.008 (0.319)	0.014 (0.001)	0.008 (0.018)	0.008 (0.064)	0.046 (0.021)
θ_2	0.980 (0.000)	0.000 (1.000)	0.978 (0.000)	0.988 (0.000)	0.975 (0.000)	0.988 (0.000)	0.989 (0.000)	0.561 (0.037)
$\log L$	- 13444.	- 14786.	- 10634.	- 12514.	- 11723.	- 12606.	- 12833.	- 13321.
	1	0	4	3	5	8	0	5

Notes: The table presents the estimates of the VARMA-DCC GARCH models for each commodity futures return with the stock market (BSE100). Variables are ordered as BSE100 and Commodity returns, that is L_{i1} and L_{i2} represent lags of BSE and commodities in i^{th} equation, respectively. P-values are given in parentheses.

Table 5:VARMA-DCC GARCH Model Estimates (Exchange and Commodities)

Variable	RCO	RNG	RGD	RSR	RAL	RZC	RLD	RNL
Mean Model (FX)								
μ_{10}	0.002 (0.746)	0.002 (0.795)	0.000 (0.957)	0.002 (0.684)	0.001 (0.901)	0.001 (0.849)	0.002 (0.715)	0.002 (0.754)
L_{11}	0.022 (0.189)	0.021 (0.201)	0.017 (0.340)	0.019 (0.238)	0.022 (0.193)	0.025 (0.179)	0.023 (0.183)	0.021 (0.214)
L_{12}	0.005 (0.086)	0.005 (0.002)	0.021 (0.012)	-0.010 (0.009)	0.009 (0.062)	-0.003 (0.347)	-0.002 (0.616)	-0.003 (0.486)
Mean Model (Commodities)								
μ_{20}	0.085 (0.030)	0.035 (0.464)	0.034 (0.021)	0.008 (0.725)	0.027 (0.123)	0.037 (0.224)	0.041 (0.197)	0.017 (0.517)
L_{21}	-0.115 (0.165)	-0.079 (0.454)	-0.037 (0.356)	-0.027 (0.597)	-0.063 (0.179)	-0.121 (0.036)	-0.082 (0.119)	-0.056 (0.345)
L_{22}	0.012 (0.508)	-0.020 (0.332)	-0.017 (0.440)	0.006 (0.719)	-0.013 (0.449)	0.005 (0.769)	0.004 (0.808)	-0.020 (0.478)
Variance Equation								
C_{11}	0.006 (0.000)	0.006 (0.001)	0.004 (0.073)	0.005 (0.001)	0.003 (0.020)	0.005 (0.001)	0.004 (0.014)	0.008 (0.000)
C_{21}	0.131 (0.000)	0.123 (0.014)	0.055 (0.123)	0.040 (0.029)	0.040 (0.335)	0.035 (0.004)	0.017 (0.073)	0.629 (0.091)
C_{22}	0.140 (0.000)	0.143 (0.000)	0.131 (0.000)	0.147 (0.000)	0.146 (0.000)	0.142 (0.000)	0.147 (0.000)	0.145 (0.000)
α_{11}	0.000 (0.087)	0.000 (0.721)	0.002 (0.480)	0.000 (0.020)	0.000 (0.432)	0.000 (0.709)	0.000 (0.482)	0.001 (0.200)
α_{12}	0.257 (0.051)	-0.032 (0.818)	0.038 (0.639)	0.001 (0.992)	-0.074 (0.231)	0.114 (0.059)	0.188 (0.144)	0.019 (0.923)
α_{21}	0.116 (0.000)	0.068 (0.000)	0.116 (0.028)	0.063 (0.000)	0.073 (0.002)	0.044 (0.001)	0.011 (0.107)	0.196 (0.041)
α_{22}	0.836 (0.000)	0.835 (0.000)	0.841 (0.000)	0.833 (0.000)	0.821 (0.000)	0.836 (0.000)	0.827 (0.000)	0.831 (0.000)
β_{11}	0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.831)	0.001 (0.806)	0.000 (0.197)	0.003 (0.055)	0.000 (0.772)	0.001 (0.256)	-0.001 (0.072)
β_{12}	-0.329 (0.014)	0.038 (0.817)	0.036 (0.731)	0.014 (0.921)	0.163 (0.160)	-0.163 (0.015)	-0.230 (0.103)	-0.082 (0.783)
β_{21}	0.868 (0.000)	0.922 (0.000)	0.821 (0.000)	0.923 (0.000)	0.895 (0.000)	0.948 (0.000)	0.986 (0.000)	0.681 (0.000)
θ_1	0.004 (0.027)	0.008 (0.230)	0.017 (0.006)	0.006 (0.206)	0.001 (0.670)	0.004 (0.064)	0.003 (0.031)	0.005 (0.001)
θ_2	0.994 (0.000)	0.892 (0.000)	0.967 (0.014)	0.988 (0.000)	0.994 (0.000)	0.993 (0.000)	0.996 (0.000)	0.995 (0.000)
Log L	-9662.8	-10952.8	-6829.4	-8699.4	-7838.9	-8810.5	-9001.9	-9540.4

Notes: The table presents the estimates of the VARMA-DCC GARCH models for each commodity futures return with the Exchange market (FX). Variables are ordered as FX and Commodity returns, that is L_{i1} and L_{i2} represent lags of FX and commodities in i^{th} equation, respectively. P-values are given in parentheses.

Table 6: VARMA-DCC GARCH Model Estimates (Bond Market and Commodities)

Variable	RCO	RNG	RGD	RSR	RAL	RZC	RLD	RNL
Mean Model (LBI)								
μ_{10}	0.028 (0.000)	0.027 (0.000)	0.027 (0.000)	0.027 (0.000)	0.028 (0.000)	0.028 (0.000)	0.027 (0.000)	0.027 (0.000)
L_{11}	0.157 (0.000)	0.169 (0.000)	0.168 (0.000)	0.166 (0.000)	0.166 (0.000)	0.167 (0.000)	0.165 (0.000)	0.167 (0.000)
L_{12}	-0.011 (0.000)	-0.002 (0.110)	0.000 (0.984)	-0.006 (0.039)	-0.014 (0.000)	-0.011 (0.000)	-0.008 (0.000)	-0.006 (0.005)
Mean Model (Commodities)								
μ_{20}	0.086 (0.001)	0.055 (0.069)	0.033 (0.037)	0.002 (0.927)	0.027 (0.187)	0.031 (0.198)	0.036 (0.111)	0.007 (0.780)
L_{21}	-0.013 (0.896)	-0.023 (0.834)	0.032 (0.590)	0.042 (0.654)	0.047 (0.558)	0.039 (0.644)	0.251 (0.003)	0.064 (0.601)
L_{22}	0.003 (0.852)	-0.011 (0.504)	-0.007 (0.700)	-0.008 (0.657)	-0.012 (0.469)	0.012 (0.524)	0.019 (0.227)	-0.019 (0.508)
Variance Equation								
C_{11}	0.001 (0.000)	0.002 (0.003)	0.001 (0.124)	0.001 (0.047)	0.002 (0.004)	0.002 (0.025)	0.002 (0.000)	0.001 (0.402)
C_{21}	0.100 (0.000)	0.040 (0.001)	0.061 (0.102)	0.021 (0.006)	0.044 (0.470)	0.022 (0.078)	0.041 (0.000)	0.618 (0.206)
C_{22}	0.120 (0.000)	0.132 (0.000)	0.128 (0.000)	0.123 (0.000)	0.135 (0.000)	0.139 (0.000)	0.136 (0.000)	0.132 (0.000)
α_{11}	0.000 (0.013)	0.000 (0.336)	0.000 (0.737)	0.000 (0.874)	0.000 (0.950)	0.000 (0.495)	0.000 (0.032)	0.000 (0.863)
α_{12}	0.360 (0.029)	0.360 (0.009)	0.046 (0.780)	0.600 (0.002)	-0.006 (0.950)	0.273 (0.016)	0.010 (0.388)	-0.118 (0.002)
α_{21}	0.106 (0.000)	0.069 (0.000)	0.111 (0.009)	0.035 (0.002)	0.071 (0.059)	0.041 (0.014)	0.044 (0.000)	0.199 (0.081)
α_{22}	0.874 (0.000)	0.861 (0.000)	0.863 (0.000)	0.869 (0.000)	0.858 (0.000)	0.856 (0.000)	0.858 (0.000)	0.859 (0.000)
β_{11}	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.604)	0.000 (0.792)	0.000 (0.551)	0.000 (0.873)	0.000 (0.288)	0.000 (0.155)	0.000 (0.470)
β_{12}	-0.265 (0.069)	-0.364 (0.002)	0.247 (0.421)	-0.585 (0.004)	0.094 (0.622)	-0.270 (0.006)	0.254 (0.000)	0.676 (0.285)
β_{21}	0.878 (0.000)	0.930 (0.000)	0.804 (0.000)	0.958 (0.000)	0.900 (0.000)	0.953 (0.000)	0.935 (0.000)	0.661 (0.001)
θ_1	0.015 (0.122)	0.001 (0.757)	0.005 (0.311)	0.002 (0.502)	0.000 (0.763)	0.006 (0.230)	0.001 (0.270)	0.014 (0.018)
θ_2	0.915 (0.000)	0.892 (0.000)	0.983 (0.000)	0.946 (0.000)	0.998 (0.000)	0.934 (0.000)	0.999 (0.000)	0.956 (0.000)
$\log L$	-7896.3	-8466.7	-5092.9	-6873.1	-6085.9	-7057.7	-7243.0	-7794.4

Notes: The table presents the estimates of the VARMA-DCC GARCH models for each commodity futures return with the Bond market (LBI). Variables are ordered as LBI and Commodity returns, that is L_{i1} and L_{i2} represent lags of LBI and commodities in i^{th} equation, respectively. P-values are given in parentheses.

Precious Metals: Gold demonstrates appreciable negative correlation with BSE100 for most of the sample, confirming its safe-haven role [2]. Its bond market correlation is also predominantly negative. The forex-Gold correlation is mainly positive, reflecting exchange rate pass-through on the rupee-denominated gold price. Silver mirrors Gold's safe-haven characteristics vis-à-vis the Forex and bond markets.

Base Metals: Aluminium, Zinc, Lead, and Nickel show predominantly positive correlations with BSE100, limiting their hedging appeal for equity investors. However, Zinc, Lead, and Nickel display negative forex correlations (particularly in 2010), and Aluminium and Lead are strongly negatively correlated with the Bond Market throughout the period.

Figure 2: Dynamic Conditional Correlations from the DCC Model

The DCC correlations are considerably larger than unconditional correlations during crisis periods (2008-09, COVID-19), underscoring the inadequacy of static measures. This differential behaviour reflects the participation of financial investors in commodity markets, confirming financialization, albeit at a lower degree than in developed countries, as also observed for China [12].

5.4 Time-Varying Hedge Ratios and Portfolio Weights

Following [33], Figure 3 shows that hedge ratios are highly variable during crisis periods and comparatively stable otherwise, with major fluctuations during 2008-09 and COVID-19. For the stock market, Gold and Natural Gas display predominantly negative hedge ratios, supporting the safe-haven hypothesis. In the forex market, positions are reversed: Crude Oil, Silver, Zinc, Nickel, and Lead show negative hedge ratios, making them effective forex hedges. The mean hedge ratios of Natural Gas and Gold vis-à-vis the stock market are -0.031 and -0.089 , respectively (Table 8). Bond market hedge ratios with commodity futures are predominantly negative and stable, suggesting that most commodity futures can serve as bond market hedges.

Table 7: Summary statistics of Dynamic Conditional Correlations

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
BSE_CO	0.111	0.099	0.647	-0.279	0.101	-0.083	5.159
FX_CO	-0.007	0.007	0.118	-0.161	0.055	-0.487	2.848
BM_CO	-0.063	-0.063	0.282	-0.366	0.035	0.466	25.988
BSE_NG	-0.011	-0.011	0.462	-0.254	0.035	1.401	26.130
FX_NG	0.073	0.073	0.171	-0.045	0.016	-0.338	9.449
BM_NG	-0.030	-0.030	0.034	-0.076	0.004	3.704	80.131
BSE_GD	-0.095	-0.096	0.184	-0.402	0.097	-0.212	3.125
FX_GD	0.072	0.066	0.321	-0.205	0.077	0.204	3.522
BM_GD	-0.012	-0.011	0.128	-0.228	0.033	-1.067	10.368
BSE_SR	0.055	0.064	0.275	-0.184	0.079	0.040	2.442
FX_SR	-0.037	-0.040	0.121	-0.239	0.051	0.051	3.972
BM_SR	-0.003	-0.003	0.124	-0.145	0.013	-0.617	39.312
BSE_AL	0.078	0.070	0.406	-0.260	0.086	0.186	5.366
FX_AL	0.010	0.012	0.030	-0.023	0.009	-1.466	5.273
BM_AL	-0.042	-0.043	-0.026	-0.070	0.006	-0.312	3.569
BSE_ZC	0.123	0.122	0.338	-0.189	0.082	-0.737	4.498
FX_ZC	-0.027	-0.019	0.069	-0.164	0.045	-0.841	3.050
BM_ZC	-0.015	-0.015	0.120	-0.110	0.020	1.044	13.013
BSE_LD	0.112	0.097	0.331	-0.153	0.075	-0.206	3.542
FX_LD	-0.048	-0.043	0.029	-0.180	0.044	-0.717	2.821
BM_LD	-0.034	-0.033	0.003	-0.077	0.016	-0.339	2.037
BSE_NL	0.100	0.099	0.622	-0.368	0.055	0.641	23.081
FX_NL	-0.059	-0.043	0.234	-0.244	0.060	-0.402	2.927
BM_NL	-0.019	-0.019	0.175	-0.298	0.043	-0.385	8.407

The portfolio weights fluctuate substantially during and after the global financial crisis, with the highest fluctuations for commodity/stock portfolios and the lowest for commodity/bond portfolios. The mean weight for BSE/Gold is 0.425, implying a substantial Gold allocation is needed to diversify equity portfolio risk. See Appendix Figures 4-5 and Table 9 for the time-varying portfolio weight plots and summary statistics.

6 Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study investigated the financialization of Indian commodity futures markets using daily data from April 3, 2006 to March 31, 2022, covering eight commodity futures and three

financial market indices, analysed using the VARMA-DCC-GARCH model. The model provides evidence of financialization of Indian commodity futures markets; however, the degree as reflected in low correlations and selective volatility spillovers is not as strong as in developed markets, consistent with observations from other emerging economies [12].

Figure 3: Time-Varying Hedge Ratios

Based on these findings, following policy implications could be suggested.

1. The evidence of *moderate financialization* suggests that governments need not impose restrictive regulations on financial investments in Indian commodity futures markets.

A regulatory environment that supports financial participation can enhance market liquidity and price discovery.

2. The limited integration of commodity futures with other financial markets implies that portfolio managers can benefit from diversification. Gold and Natural Gas offer effective equity and bond market hedges, while base metals provide diversification opportunities in the forex market.
3. Spillover and dynamic conditional correlation results indicate that investors must closely monitor the time-varying risks associated with hedging strategies, as correlations and hedge effectiveness change significantly across market regimes and crisis episodes.
4. *Gold functions as a safe-haven asset*, maintaining negative or near-zero correlations with equity and bond markets even during the 2008–09 Global Financial Crisis and COVID-19. Commodity futures more broadly can serve as diversifiers in well-structured portfolios.
5. The time-varying and asymmetric nature of hedge ratios underscores the need for *dynamic portfolio strategies*. Static hedging approaches are inadequate for capturing evolving market dynamics, particularly during crises when hedging is needed most.

Table 8: Summary statistics of Hedge ratio

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
CO_BSE	0.213	0.178	1.791	-0.738	0.210	0.994	7.698
CO_FX	-0.050	0.029	0.765	-2.376	0.340	-1.949	11.019
CO_BM	-0.616	-0.539	1.074	-8.890	0.548	-5.374	59.712
NG_BSE	-0.031	-0.029	0.763	-0.829	0.087	-0.036	21.276
NG_FX	0.584	0.535	2.179	-0.126	0.283	1.063	5.168
NG_BM	-0.338	-0.279	0.102	-1.552	0.214	-1.626	6.153
GD_BSE	-0.089	-0.082	0.107	-0.493	0.091	-0.681	3.705
GD_FX	0.172	0.154	0.988	-0.469	0.186	0.428	3.893
GD_BM	-0.040	-0.042	0.548	-0.659	0.106	-0.103	6.522
SR_BSE	0.075	0.089	0.370	-0.282	0.112	-0.037	2.615
SR_FX	-0.153	-0.154	0.805	-1.499	0.243	-0.275	6.176
SR_BM	-0.020	-0.020	0.498	-0.427	0.059	0.906	28.721
AL_BSE	0.090	0.080	0.514	-0.305	0.093	-0.096	4.485
AL_FX	0.034	0.037	0.147	-0.085	0.031	-0.521	4.008
AL_BM	-0.230	-0.220	-0.031	-0.705	0.095	-0.712	4.073
ZC_BSE	0.181	0.185	0.567	-0.228	0.121	-0.242	4.110
ZC_FX	-0.108	-0.088	0.284	-0.755	0.188	-0.926	3.834
ZC_BM	-0.106	-0.098	0.440	-0.522	0.108	0.380	6.207
LD_BSE	0.174	0.160	0.616	-0.166	0.122	0.490	4.330
LD_FX	-0.217	-0.162	0.152	-1.016	0.214	-0.883	3.219
LD_BM	-0.245	-0.206	0.010	-1.151	0.147	-0.872	3.920
NL_BSE	0.178	0.177	1.110	-2.180	0.113	-3.849	81.751
NL_FX	-0.271	-0.239	12.353	-1.935	0.407	10.577	292.429
NL_BM	-0.172	-0.158	1.336	-11.996	0.421	-9.160	218.104

7 References

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Appendix

Figure 4: Time-varying portfolio weights computed from DCC Models

Figure 5: Time-varying portfolio weights computed from DCC Models

Table 9: Summary Statistics of Port-folio weights

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
BSE_CO	0.769	0.796	1.000	0.279	0.139	-0.787	3.203
FX_CO	0.944	0.964	0.999	0.692	0.053	-1.666	5.757
BM_CO	0.970	0.978	1.000	0.734	0.031	-3.173	15.969
BSE_NG	0.838	0.872	0.990	0.214	0.119	-1.762	6.710
FX_NG	0.982	0.991	1.000	0.605	0.031	-4.641	34.150
BM_NG	0.976	0.985	0.999	0.716	0.032	-3.921	21.991
BSE_GD	0.425	0.439	0.754	0.084	0.121	-0.417	2.994
FX_GD	0.850	0.873	1.000	0.509	0.090	-1.049	3.724
BM_GD	0.918	0.934	0.996	0.451	0.059	-2.042	9.489
BSE_SR	0.656	0.680	0.927	0.175	0.136	-0.987	3.953
FX_SR	0.915	0.930	0.999	0.602	0.060	-1.440	5.503
BM_SR	0.967	0.975	0.998	0.859	0.024	-1.632	5.849
BSE_AL	0.556	0.566	0.938	0.022	0.154	-0.466	3.141
FX_AL	0.891	0.917	0.994	0.417	0.077	-1.856	7.218
BM_AL	0.938	0.958	0.994	0.407	0.063	-3.148	15.466
BSE_ZC	0.680	0.692	0.924	0.120	0.137	-0.737	3.922
FX_ZC	0.916	0.943	0.993	0.527	0.082	-2.356	8.697
BM_ZC	0.963	0.977	0.999	0.683	0.042	-3.535	18.488
BSE_LD	0.707	0.707	0.950	0.431	0.100	-0.078	2.701
FX_LD	0.924	0.944	0.990	0.617	0.058	-1.937	7.301
BM_LD	0.967	0.975	0.998	0.526	0.033	-4.470	33.681
BSE_NL	0.758	0.777	1.000	0.158	0.116	-0.954	3.905
FX_NL	0.936	0.955	1.000	0.535	0.058	-2.333	10.601
BM_NL	0.973	0.984	1.000	0.131	0.041	-7.825	111.079